

RESEARCH REPORT

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Field Guide for Systematizing Information

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TREPA

**Threat Reduction for the
Environment, People, and Animals**

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FIELD GUIDE FOR SCOPING TRIP

Communities' observation

1. Basic data & practical:

1. Person completing this guide:

2. Country & area:

3. Name of the community:

4. Date of visit:

5. Duration of visit:

6. Type of visit:

a. pre-arranged meetings ()

b. spontaneous interactions with local people ()

c. observations from the car ()

7. Team members who visited:

8. Interpreter:

9. Language of the community:

10. Associated general photographs (or other data):

11. Nearby town/s:

12. GPS coordinates:

13. Accessibility (condition of roads, etc.):

14. Type of interactions generated with the community:

15. Services present in the community (drinking water, electricity, communal places, presence of the State, etc.):

16. Level of hospitality observed:

2. Observed relationship with One Health Dimensions:

1. Presence of human health centers:

2. Presence of veterinary care centers:

3. Main economic activity observed:

4. Means of transportation observed:

5. Wet markets observed:

3. Observed relationship with wildlife & IWT:

1. Wildlife observed in the surrounding area:

2. Wild or semi-domesticated wildlife observed in the community:

3. Productive domestic animals in the community:

4. Armed people in the streets:

4. Spatial relationship with other stakeholders:

1. Distance to human health centers:

2. Distance to veterinary care centers:

3. Distance to official health surveillance centers:

4. Distance and logistic relationship observed with private reserves:

5. Distance and logistic relationship observed with public reserves:
